

1 **Online supplementary material**

2 **Intrahospital supervised exercise training improves survival rate in hypertensive**
3 **COVID-19 patients**

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18 **Running Head:** intrahospital exercise and COVID-19

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31 Supplementary table S1. Hypertensive medication profile.

	HTN N = 238	HTN+EX N= 201	p-value
Thi- Azide Diuretics	n = 67 (28.15%)	n = 26 (12.93%)	0.007
Calcium Antagonist	n = 57 (23.94%)	n = 35 (17.41%)	0.236
Angiotensin Converting enzyme (ACE)	n = 27 (11.34%)	n = 18 (8.95%)	0.617
Angiotensin receptor Blockers (ARBs)	n = 92 (38.65%)	n = 64 (31.84%)	0.439
Beta-Adrenergic Blocking Agents	n = 51 (21.42%)	n = 15 (7.46%)	0.002
No medication reported	n = 2 (0.84%)	n = 0 (0.00%)	0.215

32 Data are showed as number of subject (n) and % of total patients. The medication was classified accordingly to
 33 their action mechanism. Data were analyzed using Mann-Whitney non-parametric test. A p<0.05 was considered
 34 as significant.

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55 Supplementary table S2. Pre-exercise resting parameters.

	HTN n=238		HTN+EX n=201		p-value
	F, n=94 (40%)/M, n=144 (60%)		F, n=99 (49%)/M, n=102 (51%)		
	Mean \pm SD	Min – max	Mean \pm SD	Min – max	
Age (y)	66.22 \pm 14.10	24 – 96	64.18 \pm 14.32	28 – 99	0.963
Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	36.70 \pm 0.79	35 – 39	36.73 \pm 0.73	35 – 40	0.751
Body weight (kg)	80.70 \pm 15.39	46 – 118	77.50 \pm 11.10	55 – 100	0.507
Body height (cm)	167.20 \pm 9.17	148 – 184	164.10 \pm 9.77	150 – 180	0.316
R _f (breaths/min)	24.33 \pm 7.53	10 – 59	23.45 \pm 6.53	7 – 69	0.210
SpO ₂ (%)	93.68 \pm 7.54	50 – 100	94.74 \pm 4.80	65 – 100	0.091
SBP (mmHg)	136.20 \pm 27.46	85 – 245	134.70 \pm 23.27	83 – 229	0.541
DBP (mmHg)	75.61 \pm 13.51	44 – 123	76.28 \pm 13.49	41 – 116	0.605
PP (mmHg)	60.84 \pm 22.66	19 – 140	58.40 \pm 18.32	24 – 116	0.226
MABP (mmHg)	95.80 \pm 16.03	62 – 156	95.75 \pm 15.07	60 – 154	0.971
HR (beats/min)	79.42 \pm 16.61	26 – 152	76.76 \pm 14.03	40 – 120	0.086

56 Data are showed as mean \pm standard deviation and as minimum to maximum value. HTN: hypertension; EX:
57 exercise training; F: female; M: male; R_f: respiratory frequency; SpO₂: arterial oxygen saturation; SBP: systolic blood
58 pressure; DBP: diastolic BP; PP: pulse pressure; MABP: mean arterial BP; HR: heart rate. Data were analyzed
59 using Mann-Whitney non-parametric test. A p<0.05 was considered as significant.

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75 Supplementary table S3. Exercise training (EX) intervention characteristics.

	Modality	Volume	Intensity	Frequency
Cardiopulmonary	Aerobic exercises (walk, walk in eight, military march and walk on tiptoe and heels)	10-15 minutes for first 3-4 sessions and incrementally increase. 15-45 min each session	Borg dyspnea score ≤ 4 ; scale for fatigue (must not exceed a score of 11–12)	1-2 times per day, 3-4 times a week
Breathing exercises	Diaphragmatic breathing, Pursed lip breathing, Active abdominal contraction	2-3 times / day, daily: 10-15 minutes for first 3-4 sessions	Borg dyspnea score ≤ 4 ; scale for fatigue (must not exceed a score of 11–12)	1-2 times per day, 3-4 times a week
Musculoskeletal	Musculoskeletal (Lifting dumbbells, stand up and sit, lumbar stabilization)	Resistance exercises	8–10 sets of 12–15 repetitions/week	1-2 times per day, 3-4 times a week

76 The following parameters were constantly evaluated during EX:

- 77 • Saturation: must remain above 92–93% during the whole exercise.
- 78 • Heart rate: must not increase more than 20 beats per minute from the baseline heart rate during
79 mild intensity exercise (patient’s pharmacological therapy should also be carefully considered,
80 especially the use of beta-blockers that limit the physiological increase in frequency during
81 exercise).
- 82 • Systolic blood pressure: must be ≥ 90 mmHg and ≤ 180 mmHg
- 83 • Symptomatology: with use of the Borg scale for dyspnea (must not exceed a score of 4) and of
84 the rate of perceived exertion (RPE) scale for fatigue (must not exceed a score of 11–12).

85 The exercise training protocol was based on previous recommendations¹.

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References

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